

Thiodiazines. Part III. Hydroxythiodiazines.

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In continuation of the investigation of 1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazines it has been found that certain α -halogenated esters of aliphatic acids condense with benzyl- or nitrobenzyl-dithiocarbazines which contain the skeleton $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{N} = \text{C}(\text{SH})-$, necessary for the synthesis of the 1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine ring-system (*cf.* this *Journal*, 1924, 1, 53; *ibid.*, 1925, 2, 95). The condensation, which is best carried out in alcoholic solution in presence of pyridine or the calculated quantity of ammonia, hardly takes place in absence of these condensing agents, which evidently act by eliminating hydrobromic acid.

Condensation of benzyldithiocarbazine with α -bromo-*isobutyric* and α -bromo-*n*-butyric esters, however, did not take place even when these substances were boiled with alcoholic ammonia.

The thiodiazines obtained are well-defined crystalline bodies, neutral to litmus but soluble in cold alkali: they are precipitated from the alkaline solution by mineral

acids as should be expected from the hydroxylic structure (I) given above,

An attempt was made to obtain 2-thiol-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine (II) by the condensation of potassium dithiocarbazinate and monochloroacetic ester, thus :

The reaction, doubtless, takes place in an alcoholic solution of the components at the ordinary temperature; but the isolation of the mercaptan from the reaction mixture in a pure condition proved unsuccessful. The disulphide of (II) was, however, easily obtained on keeping the reaction mixture exposed to air for several hours. An attempt to reduce this compound to the mercaptan (II) was unsuccessful.

When chloroacetic acid is added to a solution of potassium dithiocarbazinate the principal product of reaction is 2-thiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole-5-thiolacetic acid.

The formation of this compound is interesting in view of the fact that methods for obtaining it from 2:5-dithiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole and chloroacetic acid have been fruitless (Rây, Guha and Das, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1309).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Thiobenzyl-5-hydroxy-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine.

One mol. of benzyldithiocarbazinate (Busch, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1916, [ii] 93, 25), which is best crystallised from hot xylene, was dissolved in warm alcohol, slightly more than one mol. of monochloro acetic ester added and then one mol. of alcoholic ammonia was run in with constant shaking. Reaction took place with rise of temperature and within a few minutes crystals of ammonium chloride began to separate. After an hour the product was diluted with water when a reddish brown oil was precipitated which solidified. This was collected, dried on porous porcelain, dissolved in cold benzene and filtered. The filtrate was diluted with ligroin when colourless rhombic plates of *2-thiobenzyl-5-hydroxy-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine* were obtained. After recrystallisation from a mixture of benzene and ligroin it melted at 123-24°. The yield was quantitative. The ammonia can be replaced by pyridine, but in this case, in order to ensure complete reaction, it was found necessary to heat the mixture under reflux for 15 to 20 minutes. (Found: N=11·94. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2S_2$ requires N=11·77 per cent.).

It is easily soluble in alcohol, benzene, ether, pyridine and acetic acid, insoluble in ligroin. On adding warm caustic soda (8·9 per cent.) it dissolves and on cooling the solution deposits beautiful slender needles of the *sodium salt* which is hygroscopic and very soluble in alcohol or acetone. On benzoylation of the compound by the Schotten-Baumann method a yellow semi-solid mass was obtained. It solidified on cooling below 0° and was insoluble in alkali and very soluble in most organic solvents. It slowly decomposed in presence of water or alkali and therefore could not be obtained pure for analysis. Benzoylation in pyridine solution gave no better result.

2-Thiobenzyl-5-methoxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine.—Molecular proportions of 2-thiobenzyl-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine, caustic soda (5 per cent. aqueous solution) and methyl iodide were heated together on the water-bath under reflux until the methyl iodide had disappeared. The resulting oil was extracted using ether, the ethereal solution was shaken with dilute caustic soda solution to remove any unchanged hydroxythiodiazine, washed several times with water, and dried by calcium chloride. The ether was removed under reduced pressure. Obtained in this manner, the methoxy derivative formed a thick, pale brown oil with a peculiar strong odour. (Found: C=52.10; H=5.06. $C_{11}H_{13}ON_2S_2$ requires C=52.38; H=4.76 per cent.)

o-Nitrobenzyl dithiocarbazinate.—The method of preparation is practically the same as given by Busch for the benzyl derivative (*loc. cit.*). Hydrazine hydrate (5 g.) and a 10 per cent. alcoholic solution of caustic potash (56 c.c.) were mixed and the mixture was cooled to 0°. Carbon disulphide (7.6 g.) was gradually run in so that the temperature of the reaction mixture did not rise above 25°. *o*-Nitrobenzylchloride (12 g.) was then added and the mixture shaken at the room temperature for about an hour, the temperature of the reaction mixture being not allowed to rise above 50°. On adding water to the reaction mixture an oil was precipitated which solidified on cooling. From benzene it separated in pale-yellow glistening plates which melted at 94° after shrinking at 92°. It was easily soluble in alcohol, acetone, hot benzene or aqueous alkalis but almost insoluble in ligroin. (Found: S=26.74. $C_8H_9O_2S_2N_3$ requires S=26.37 per cent.)

2-Thio-o-nitrobenzyl-5-hydroxy-1:3:4-thiodiazine, from ethyl chloracetate and *o*-nitrobenzyl dithiocarbazinate, formed transparent needles melting at 151°. It

was sparingly soluble in benzene and alcohol but could be easily crystallised from acetone and water. (Found: $N=14.97$. $C_{10}H_9O_3N_3S_2$ requires $N=14.84$ per cent.).

2-Thio-p-nitrobenzyl-5-hydroxy-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine was obtained from *p*-nitrobenzylidithiocarbazine and ethyl chloroacetate in quantitative yield. It was sparingly soluble in alcohol or benzene but easily dissolved in pyridine or acetone. From a mixture of acetone and benzene it was obtained as long, white, slender needles melting at 173° . (Found: $N=14.96$. $C_{10}H_9O_3N_3S_2$ requires $N=14.84$ per cent.).

2-Thiobenzyl-5-hydroxy-6-methyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine was obtained from α -bromopropionic ester and benzylidithiocarbazine. It separated from a mixture of benzene and ligroin in colourless crystals which melted at $110-111^\circ$. (Found: $N=11.21$. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_3S_2$ requires $N=11.11$ per cent.).

2-Thiobenzyl-5-hydroxy-6-carbethoxy-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine.—Molecular proportions of benzyl dithiocarbazine, bromomalonic ester and alcoholic ammonia were heated together on the water-bath for a few minutes and allowed to stand for several hours. On adding water to the product an oil separated which partly solidified after some time. This was collected and pressed on porous plate: it crystallised from benzene after treatment with animal charcoal in colourless needles melting at $116-117^\circ$. (Found: $N=9.14$. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_3S_2$ requires $N=9.03$ per cent.).

2-Thiol-5-hydroxy-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine-disulphide—Hydrazine hydrate (100 per cent., 5 g.) was added to a solution of caustic potash (5.6 g.) dissolved in alcohol (60 c.c.). The mixture was cooled to 0° , carbon bisulphide (7.6 g.) was gradually added when a straw-colored oil separated out. Ethyl chloroacetate (11.5 g.) was then

poured into the mixture which was thoroughly shaken for a few minutes and kept at the ordinary temperature for about 2 hours. The precipitated potassium chloride was removed, and the filtrate was exposed to air. The crystalline residue, which contained some ethyl chloroacetate and other oily impurities, was dried on porous plate and twice recrystallised from hot benzene or alcohol from which it separated in pale yellow, ferny crystals melting at 92°. The yield of the *disulphide* of 2-thiol-5-hydroxy-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine was about 45 per cent. (Found: N=18.89; S=43.30. $C_6H_6O_2N_2S_4$ requires N=18.92; S=43.54 per cent.).

It was a fairly strong acid and decomposed sodium bicarbonate in the cold. It gave a pale yellow precipitate with mercuric chloride but not with lead acetate; it scarcely decolorised a solution of iodine. It was soluble in hot water, insoluble in light petroleum but very soluble in pyridine, acetone and glacial acetic acid.

Reduction of the Disulphide.—The disulphide, dissolved in sodium carbonate solution, was reduced by means of the aluminium-mercury couple. The reduction product was isolated as a lead salt, and was ultimately obtained as a brown viscous oil. Analysis showed that it was not the desired substance.

2-Thiol-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazole-5-thiolacetic Acid.—A mixture of 5.6 gms. of caustic potash (10 per cent. in alcohol) and 5 gms. of hydrazine hydrate (100 per cent.) was cooled with ice and to the mixture were gradually added 7.6 g. of carbon disulphide and finally 8.5 g. of chloroacetic acid. The mixture was well-shaken and allowed to stand for about two hours at the ordinary temperature during which period evolution of H_2S was noticed. The mixture of potassium chloride and the *potassium salt* of 2-thiol-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazole-5-thiolacetic acid, which had separated, was collected and crystallised from hot water

to remove potassium chloride. The potassium salt was dried and extracted with hot benzene to remove a small quantity of the disulphide (*vide supra*) and the residue twice crystallised from hot water containing a little alcohol when long, silky needles melting and decomposing at $252\text{--}53^\circ$ were obtained (6 g.). The potassium salt contains one mol. of water of crystallisation. (Found: $K=14\cdot63$; $S=36\cdot45$; loss of water at $130^\circ=7\cdot00$. $C_4H_3O_2S_3N_2K$, H_2O requires $K=14\cdot78$; $S=36\cdot00$; $H_2O=6\cdot82$ per cent.). It was easily soluble in hot water but insoluble in most organic media.

The free mercaptan, 2-thiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole-5-thiol-acetic acid was obtained by acidifying an aqueous solution of the potassium salt with hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from hot water in pale yellow, glistening plates melting at 164° . It was very soluble in alcohol, ether, acetone or glacial acetic acid and insoluble in benzene or ligroin. (Found: $S=46\cdot85$; $N=13\cdot25$. $C_4H_4O_2N_2S_3$ requires $S=46\cdot15$; $N=13\cdot46$ per cent.).

The aqueous solution of the mercaptan on being treated with iodine solution gave a crystalline precipitate of the *disulphide* which separated from a large quantity of alcohol in microscopic needles melting and decomposing at 180° . It possessed acidic properties. (Found: $N=13\cdot56$. $(C_4H_3O_2N_2S_3)_2$ requires $N=13\cdot53$ per cent.).

My best thanks are due to Sir P. C. Rây who has taken a keen interest in the progress of the investigation.

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Received, December 22, 1925.